

Increasing Data Sharing for Re-Use

An implementation project for the Institutional Underpinnings Program

Project summary report

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February 2023

About the Institutional Underpinnings Program

In partnership with 25 Australian universities, we created a jointly-agreed Research Data Management Framework for Institutions for the management, sharing, retention and disposal of research data. Each partner university conducted projects to validate and test an aspect of the framework in their local contexts. This is a report on one of the projects.

More information

View more outputs of the [Institutional Underpinnings program](#).

View the [Research Data Management Framework for Institutions](#).

Project Summary

As of December 2022, the project is still in the second phase of development, with the Library and Research Services teams in the process of implementing the data sharing and re-use element into the Edith Cowan University (ECU) Research Development Framework. The three project goals are to:

- Develop a Data Champions Network
- Identify impediments to data sharing and reuse within the University
- Develop educational and training materials

To oversee and support the attainment of ECU project goals, a 10-member Research Data Management (RDM) Steering Group was established. The steering group has recommended stakeholder groups across the University to be contacted to identify Data Champions and also identified impediments to data sharing which will be tested further.

1. Develop Data Champion Network

The first goal of the project is to develop a Data Champion network at ECU to advocate best practices in RDM. The profile of a Data Champion was established as:

- Researchers with experience in managing either qualitative or quantitative research data
- Those with particular interest in data sharing and re-use
- Interested and willing to participate in open science / open research
- Promote FAIR data principles
- Mentoring other researchers
- Interested in conducting data management workshops
- Disciplinary representation in RDM forums and workshops

Advantages of becoming a Data Champion (DC):

- Opportunity for networking with RDM enthusiasts and share knowledge
- Increase your impact by being more visible on the DC forum
- Training on workshop creation and delivery
- Opportunity to make RDM recommendations at ECU

- Become an RDM expert
- Opportunity to learn new skills
- Multidisciplinary collaboration
- A medium to share experience and progress

The risks of the DC program were identified as lack of nominees, less participation due to lack of incentives, insufficient funding and DCs interested only in the training aspect not promotion.

The DC program was promoted through numerous channels including Associate Deans of Research in all schools, internal newsletters, Early and Mid-Career Researcher Network and the Support, Opportunities, Advice, Resources (SOAR) Centre. The promotion was successful with nine Data Champions identified across five of the eight schools at ECU.

Data Champions have highlighted aspects outlined in the Open Research and Data Publication element, that the benefits of data sharing must be highlighted, metrics on downloads and citations from the institutional repository be utilised to promote sharing, and that adequate and timely educational material is available. An additional point that has been highlighted is the need for regular touchpoints over the research lifecycle as currently communication occurs at the start and end of a research project, but it is during the project where data sharing also needs to be highlighted.

2. Impediments to Data Sharing

To identify the impediments to data sharing and reuse at ECU, a survey was sent to 103 research students. These students had previously said they would share their data as part of the initial ethics approval process, but then declined to share their data when contacted by the Library post project. The survey utilised some of the key challenges highlighted in the Open Research and Data Publication element and impediments highlighted by the steering group including lack of relevant information for publishing data, concern that data could be misinterpreted, complex policies and licences, data security, impact on research advancement, cost to publish, competitive disadvantage, publishing priority and commercial gain with no consent. The survey invited participants to be a Data Champion and sought feedback on preferred formats for educational materials (eg, webinars, face-to-face training, workshops, seminars etc).

Feedback from the survey was utilised in identifying educational and training materials to better support researchers.

3. Develop educational and training materials

ECU's Learning Management System (LMS) Canvas has been identified as the platform to host educational and training materials. The learning materials will focus on addressing the impediments in data sharing and reuse and will be developed in consultation with the Data Champions and will focus on the elements in the diagram below. Links to these educational materials will also be incorporated into

the university Research Ethics Management System (REMS) to ensure staff understand data sharing requirements from the very start of their research project.

Figure: Learning materials elements focused on.

Resulting Improvements

While the project is at its mid-way point the Data Champion program has brought together the expertise and knowledge of researchers from various schools, thus resulting in a collaborative approach to change the RDM culture. The survey of research students identified impediments in sharing data and learning materials that will be developed in consultation with Data Champions. Data Champions will then advocate the best practices in RDM.

Next Steps

The management of the DC program is expected to include:

- Planned sustainable activities for DC program across ECU on a regular basis.
- Regular promotional activities to garner interest.
- Special events on RDM to coincide with the International Data Week.
- Establishment of a DC badge which could be a recognition for their work in RDM.
- Conduct regular feedback sessions after implementing new measures.
- Establish replacement DC strategies if someone plans to leave.
- Maintain momentum.
- Measure the scale of activity every two months.

A virtual forum has been created for the Data Champions which will be the channel for announcements and act as a setting to exchange information on best practices and current insights in RDM across various disciplines.

The DCs will be meeting once every month to discuss RDM matters and also present their work.

All the educational materials for RDM will be developed in consultation with the DCs by requesting their feedback.

Project Outputs

Reusable outputs produced include:

1. A framework to establish Data Champions:

Figure: Establishing Data Champions framework.

2. Impediments for data sharing and reuse identified as part of early stages of consultation:

- Availability of information for data publishing
- Timeliness

- Erroneous data
- Complex policies and licences
- Data safety
- Impact on research advancement
- Cost of publishing
- Competitive disadvantage
- Publishing priority
- Commercial gain with no consent

3. Elements of focus for learning materials in data sharing and reuse. Once these materials have been finalised these resources will be made available for sharing.

Contact the Scholarly Communication Team for access to resources via email researchonline@ecu.edu.au

View more outputs of the [Institutional Underpinnings program](#).